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CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND PROFITABILITY OF ANDHRA PRADESH STATE FINANCIAL CORPORATION: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

*** DR. P. SAHJEEVI**

ABSTRACT:

Capital structure is most significant discipline of firms' operations. Capital structure determination constitutes a difficult that involves several antagonistic factors. Profitability is the main factor for the consideration at the time of designing the capital structure of a firm. The purpose of this paper is to examine the extent to which growth determines the capital structure and profitability performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation. This is done by examining some component of capital structure in relation to APSPFC and then testing the resulting ideas empirically. This paper may provide useful insights for the interested parties, such as owners, investors etc.

Key words: Capital Structure, shareholders' Fund, Debt Fund, Leverages, Working capital, Profitability.

INTRODUCTION :

To understand how companies finance their operations, it is necessary to examine the determinants of their financing or capital structure decisions. Company financing decisions involve a wide range of policy issues. Successful organization has always been dependent on factors such as availability of entrepreneurship, efficient production techniques, and skillful management methods and above all, adequate financial resources.

In this view of capital structure formation to the firms, the financial institutions are necessarily promoting new industries and catering to the medium and long-term capital needs of the existing industries for their expansion and modernization gave birth to the concept of development banking. Development financial institutions and banks have been conceived and adapted to fill in the institutional void by many underdeveloped and developing countries of the world to promote and accelerate their economic growth. They are addressed not to compete with other agencies of industrial finance and are required to satisfy themselves before sanctioning loans that the funds are not available to the borrowing party from any other source on reasonable terms.

The idea of establishing specialized institutions for the provision of finance for industry was given by different commissions and committees long before independence and finally took concrete shape with the establishment of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation. It is lending institution established in 1956 for promoting small and medium scale industries in Andhra Pradesh under the provisions of the State Financial Corporations Act, 1951. The Corporation came into existence on 1-11-1956 by merger of Andhra State Financial Corporation and Hyderabad State Financial Corporation. The corporation has launched many entrepreneur-friendly schemes to provide term loans, working capital term loans and special and seed capital assistance to suit the needs of various categories of entrepreneurs. The Corporation has completed five decades of dedicated service in industrial financing of tiny, small and medium scale sector units and contributing to the balanced regional development of the state.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY:

Collection of Data and Its Analysis Method: The present study is based on the secondary data extracted from the annual reports of APSPFC from 2003-04 to 2012-13, from which financial structure of the corporation has been taken. The collected data were analyzed by using statistical tools and techniques namely Correlation and Regression Analysis. In order to get the results, statistical software such as MS-Excel and SPSS has been used. Charts and Figures had been prepared for presenting and simplifying the process of analysis.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

Main objectives of the study are as follows

- ❖ To study and analyze the financial structure of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- ❖ To know the Capital Structure Performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- ❖ To Identify Impact of profitability on Capital Structure of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.

HYPOTHESES:

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

- ❖ There is no Impact of Capital structure towards the EPS of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- ❖ There is no Impact of Capital Structure Leverage towards the Return on Investment of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- ❖ There is no Impact of Working Capital towards the Return on Investment of Andhra Pradesh State Corporation

CAPITAL STRUCTURE OF APSPFC:

Capital structures consists of share capital i.e. Equity Shares, Reserves & Surplus and Debt Funds. The trend of capital structure is analyzed in three parts i.e. Shareholders' Funds, Loan Funds and Capital Employed.

Table-1: Total Equity of APSPFC

(Rs. In Lakhs)

Year	Share Capital	Reserves & Surplus	Total Equity	Growth Rate
2003-04	8,971.99 (81.66)	2,014.75 (18.34)	10,986.74 (100)	-
2004-05	9,221.99 (82)	2,014.75 (18)	11,236.74 (100)	2.27
2005-06	9,221.99 (82)	2,014.75 (18)	11,236.74 (100)	-
2006-07	9,221.99 (81)	2,157.50 (12)	11,379.49 (100)	1.25
2007-08	20,600.99 (88.5)	2,676.40 (11.5)	23,277.39 (100)	104.55
2008-09	20,600.99 (74)	6,961.43 (26)	27,562.42 (100)	18.4
2009-10	20,600.99 (60)	13,729.37 (40)	34,330.36 (100)	24.52
2010-11	20,600.99 (53)	18,317.03 (47)	38,918.02 (100)	13.36
2011-12	20,600.99 (49)	21,140.46 (51)	41,741.45 (100)	7.25
2012-13	20,600.99 (47)	23,567.6 (53)	44,168.61 (100)	5.81

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2002-04 to 2012-13.

The Table No. 1 shows that the share capital of the APSFC has been increased during the year 2002 to 2013 due to the issue of equity shares from the year 2007-08. It is seen from the year 2007-08 Reserves and surplus are all so increased, these are the reasons shareholders fund has shown an increasing trend during the study period.

Table 2: Loan funds of APSFC (Rs. in Lakhs)

Year	Long term borrowings	Loan pending conversion to share capital	Total debt	Growth Rate
2002-04	99,795.64 (98.7%)	1,334.00 (1.3%)	101,129.64 (100%)	-
2003-05	96,452.52 (98.6%)	1,334.00 (1.4%)	97,786.52 (100%)	-3.3%
2004-06	100,198.27 (94%)	6,334.00 (6%)	106,532.27 (100%)	8.9%
2005-07	107,900.96 (94.4%)	6,334.00 (5.6%)	114,234.96 (100%)	7.4%
2006-08	136,587.69 (95.9%)	5,834.00 (4.1%)	142,421.69 (100%)	24.67%
2007-09	156,105.67 (99%)	1,334.00 (1%)	157,439.67 (100%)	10.54%
2008-10	107,768.81 (98.7%)	1,334.00 (1.3%)	109,102.81 (100%)	-30.7%
2009-11	118,732.44 (98.8%)	1,334.00 (1.2%)	120,066.44 (100%)	10.04%
2010-12	120,942.23 (98.9%)	1,334.00 (1.1%)	122,276.23 (100%)	1.84%
2011-13	112,462.69 (98.8%)	1,334.00 (1.2%)	1,13,796.69 (100%)	-6.5%

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2002-04 to 2012-13.

Table 2: Capital Employed of APSFC (Rs. in Lakhs)

Year	Shareholders' Funds	Loan Funds	Capital Employed	Growth Rate
2002-04	99,795.64 (49.6)	101,129.64 (50.4)	2,00,925.28 (100)	-
2003-05	96,452.52 (48.5)	97,786.52 (48.5)	1,94,239.04 (100)	-3.3%
2004-06	100,198.27 (48.5)	106,532.27 (51.5)	2,06,730.54 (100)	6.4
2005-07	107,900.96 (48.5)	114,234.96 (51.5)	2,22,135.9 (100)	7.3
2006-08	136,587.69 (49.8)	142,421.69 (51.1)	2,79,009.38 (100)	25.6
2007-09	156,105.67 (49.8)	157,439.67 (50.2)	3,13,545.3 (100)	12.38
2008-10	107,768.81 (49.6)	109,102.81 (50.4)	2,16,871.6 (100)	-31.8
2009-11	118,732.44 (49.7)	120,066.44 (50.3)	2,38,798.9 (100)	30.3
2010-12	120,942.23 (51.1)	122,276.23 (50.9)	2,43,218.4 (100)	2.3
2011-13	112,462.69 (46.9)	1,13,796.69 (48.9)	2,26,259.38 (100)	-4.75

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2002-04 to 2012-13.

From the Table No. 2 shows that the Debt funds of the APSFC have been increasing trend during the year 2002 to 2013. Corporation has done more borrowings and made loan pending conversion to share capital during the year 2005 to 2008, thereafter this source of debt is constant. It is seen the overall debt structure during the study period, major source of debt funds is long term borrowings.

Table 2: Capital Employed of APSFC (Rs. in Lakhs)

Figure-3, Capital Structure of AP-SFC

From the table No.3, It is clear that the solvency position of AP-SFC was an average as the proportion of shareholders funds and debt funds almost equal during the 2003 to 2010, thereafter debt funds were increased by the corporation. It is seen the changes in the capital employed are mainly affected by the changes in the debt funds.

FINANCIAL ANALYSIS:

Table-4 Financial Ratios of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation

Year	EPS	ROA	D/E Ratio	Debt Ratio	PFTO TA	Current Ratio	Cash to Total Assets
2003-04	0.067	5.01	1.01	0.845	0.33	0.50	0.004
2004-05	0.075	1.29	1.013	0.819	0.808	0.63	0.005
2005-06	0.267	2.28	1.06	0.829	0.78	0.66	0.006
2006-07	0.295	2.24	1.058	0.804	0.76	0.68	0.005
2007-08	0.434	5.80	1.04	0.7739	0.74	0.80	0.004
2008-09	0.52	2.77	1.008	1.134	1.12	1.07	0.008
2009-10	0.791	3.17	1.01	0.799	0.78	1.01	0.007
2010-11	0.787	2.84	1.01	0.989	0.98	1.11	0.006
2011-12	0.799	2.60	1.86	0.585	0.46	0.98	0.003
2012-13	0.741	2.12	2.21	0.833	0.38	0.77	0.007
Mean	0.477	3.012	1.23	0.84	0.71	0.82	0.005
SD	0.29	1.37	0.43	0.14	0.25	0.21	0.002

The Table 4 depicts the profitability, liquidity and leverage ratios of AP-SFC, which help in determining the financial position. Debt Ratio shows the participation of Loan Funds in total assets. On an average, Debt Ratio is 0.84 times, which is higher than the standard. As Proprietary Ratios is also calculated on the basis of total assets, it does not depict the ideal position. Highest and lowest proprietary Ratio was 112 times in 2008-09 and 0.33 times. The above analysis does show good solvency position of the company, as capital int. of AP-SFC is mainly contributed by Debt Funds, whereas participation of shareholders' fund is almost equal except during the year 2012-13. Average current Ratio was 0.82 in AP-SFC, which is lower than the ideal current ratio, i.e. 2 times (2:1). In the last three years of the study period i.e. 2010, 2011 and 2012, Current Ratio has decreased to 0.77 times became this situation in Total Assets; during the study period only 0.5 percent of cash of the assets has been maintained by the corporation. The corporation also depicts a sound profitable position as its Return on assets had been between 1.29 times in 2004-05 to 5.8 times in 2007-08. Average of this ratio was 3.02 times and its SD is 1.3 times during the study period. Earnings of the AP-SFC during the study period it was maximum 0.79 times in 2012-13 and minimum earnings was 0.067 times in the year 2003-04 and the average EPS was 0.477 times and its SD 1.37 times.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Correlation is concern describing the strength of relationship between two variables. In this study, the correlation co-efficient analysis is undertaken to find out the relationship between capital structure and profitability of AP-SFC. The measure of correlation is called the co-efficient of correlation. It is denoted by 'r'. This correlation results showed in Table No. 5 to Table No.7.

Table No. 5 CORRELATION

	EPS	Shareholders' Funds	Debt Funds	Capital Employed	Working Capital
EPS	1				
Shareholders' Funds	.384	1			
Debt Funds	.603	.35	1		
Capital Employed	.631	.59	.96	1	
Working Capital	.57	.73	.951	.26	1

Correlation is significant 5% level of significance

Source: Computed

From the Table 6 shows the correlation matrix for the defined variables, i.e. EPS, Shareholder Funds, Debt Funds, Capital Employed and Working Capital. It is seen EPS is positively correlated with SF, DF, CE and WC. The positive correlation between SF and EPS reveals that shareholders fund was accompanied by an increase in EPS. This is due to the SF decreasing at a fast rate, while profitability was increase at the same rate. Positive correlation between DF and EPS, it suggests that the purpose of borrowing funds could be achieved since heavy borrowings led to increase in EPS. The same trend was followed by CE. EPS positively correlated with WC, it reveals the increase the profitability.

Table No. 6 CORRELATION

	ROA	Debt Equity Ratio	Debt Ratio	Proprietary Ratio
ROA	1			
Debt Equity Ratio	-.26	1		
Debt Ratio	-.054	-.42	1	
Proprietary Ratio	-.21	-.62	0.66	1

Correlation is significant 5% level of significance

Source: Computed

From the Table 6 shows the correlation matrix for the defined variables, i.e. ROA is negatively correlated with debt equity ratio (low degree), debt ratio (low degree) and proprietary ratios (high degree). It is reveals that profitability is not significantly correlated with financial structure of the AP5IC.

Table No. 7 CORRELATION

	ROA	Current Ratio	Cash Ratio
ROA	1		
Current Ratio	-.095	1	
Cash Ratio	-.392	.394	1

Correlation is significant 5% level of significance

Source: Computed

From the Table 7 shows the correlation matrix for the defined variables, i.e. ROA is negatively correlated with debt current ratio (low degree) and cash to total assets ratio (low degree). It is found that profitability is not significantly correlated with financial structure of the corporation.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact of capital structure on the profitability of AP5IC and examine and test the explanatory power of the conventional financial structure variables of firm specific, leverage and financial ratios of capital structure. We try to apply Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression on the firm level data, with EPS and as the dependent variables and the corporate specific capital structure and financial ratios are as the independent variables.

$$EPS = b_0 + b_1 SF + b_2 DF + b_3 CE + b_4 WC + u \dots (1)$$

$$ROA = b_0 + b_1 DER + b_2 DR + b_3 PR + u \dots (2)$$

$$ROA = b_0 + b_1 CR + b_2 CATI + u \dots (3)$$

The first equation is representing capital structure ratios of different variables. Second and third equations are used to calculate the impact of financial ratios on returns, whereas, second equation determines the impact of capital structure on profitability, while third equation establishes impact of working capital on ROA. Where, SF=Shareholders, DF=Debt Funds, CE=Capital Employed, WC=Working Capital, DER=Debt Equity Ratio, DR=Debt Ratio, PR=Proprietary Ratio, CR=Current Ratio, CATI=Cash to Total Assets, u =error term, b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 are parameters and e = error term.

Table: 8

Multiple Regression Coefficients relating to Capital Structure of AP5IC

	Un Standardized B	Standardized Beta	t	Significance
Constant(EPS)	1.062		1.85	.114
Equity	-8.77	-0.55	01.72	.135
Total Debt	4.12	0.75	2.28	.045
Working Capital	0.001	0.93	2.98	.022
Standard Error of Estimate			0.17	
Coefficient determinant (Squared)			0.77	
Dependent Variable			EPS	

Source: Computed.

REGRESSION LINE:

$$EPS = 1.062 + 8.77SF + 4.12DF + 0CE + 0.001WC + u \dots (1)$$

From the table 8 indicates the unstandardized and standardized coefficients of EPS with capital structure and working capital. It can be seen that equity and working capital have positive and equity has negative relationship. It implies that equity and working capital are minor effect of profitability of the corporation, whereas, debt funds very much influences to the EPS. The unit of increase in debt funds would increase Earnings per Share by 4.12 times. This is statistically significant at the 5% level. The independent variables explain 77 percent of the variances in the dependent variables. The regression analysis also supports the correlation analysis and t-values.

Table: 9

Multiple Regression Coefficients relating to Capital Structure on profitability of APSFC

	Un Standardized B	Standardized Beta	t	Significance
Constant(ROA)	-0.546	.	-0.74	.486
Debt Equity Ratio	0.58	0.86	2.32	.059
Debt Ratio	-0.34	-0.16	-0.41	0.693
Proprietary Ratio	0.823	0.71	1.57	.17
Standard Error of Estimate	1.39			
Coefficient determinant (Squared)	0.31			
Dependent Variable	ROA			

Source: Computed.

REGRESSION LINE:

$$ROA = -0.546 + 0.580ER - 0.34DR + 0.82PR + u \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

From the table 9 indicates the unstandardized and standardized coefficients of ROA with capital structure leverage ratios. It can be seen that debt equity ratio and proprietary ratios have positive and debt ratio has negative ratio with return on investment of the APSFC during the study period. It implies that debt equity and proprietary ratios are effect of return of the corporation, whereas, debt equity ratio is influences to the ROA. The unit of increase in debt funds would increase ROA by 0.58 times. This is statistically significant at the 5% level. The independent variables explain 31 percent of the variances in the dependent variables. The regression analysis also supports the correlation analysis and t-values.

Table: 10

Multiple Regression Coefficients relating to Working Capital on profitability of APSFC

	Un Standardized B	Standardized Beta	t	Significance
Constant(ROA)	4.54	.	2.867	.018
Current Ratio	0.27	0.057	0.15	.256
Cash Ratio	-333.24	-0.38	-1.002	.349
Standard Error of Estimate	1.44			
Coefficient determinant (Squared)	0.13			
Dependent Variable	ROA			

Source: Computed.

REGRESSION LINE:

$$ROA = 4.54 + 0.27CR - 333.24CA + u \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

From the table 10 indicates the unstandardized and standardized coefficients of ROA with working capital ratios. It can be seen that current ratio has positive and cash ratio has negative ratio with return on investment of the APSFC during the study period. It implies that current ratio is effect source of returns of the corporation, whereas, current ratio is influences to the ROA. The unit of increase in working capital would increase ROA by 0.27 times. This is statistically significant at the 5% level. The independent variables explain 13 percent of the variances only in the dependent variables. The regression analysis also supports the correlation analysis and t-values.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES:

In this paper researcher has made three hypotheses based on canal model to know the capital structure and financial performance of APSFC. t-test used for computing the appropriate t value to test the correlation significance. The simplest formula for the appropriate t-value to test significance of a correlation coefficient employs the t distribution:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

The degrees of freedom for entering the t-distribution is n - 2. Table value of (10-2) i.e. 8 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 2.306 for two tailed test. The hypotheses are re-stated as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H₀): H₁ There is no impact of Capital structure towards the EPS of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.

Table 11, Correlation and t test results for EPS and Capital Structure of APSFC

	't' value	Correlation result	'r' value	Hypothesis result
Equity	0.38	Positive and insignificant	//1.71//	Accepted
Total Debt	0.60	Positive and insignificant	//2.21//	Accepted
Net Worth	0.63	Positive and insignificant	//1.32//	Accepted
Working Capital	0.67	Positive and insignificant	//1.38//	Accepted

Source: Computed

Table 11 reveals that the Correlation between EPS and Capital Structure of APSFC. It can be seen that capital structure and working capital showed positive relationship with EPS. t-test results, It is clear that the computed value of hypothesis is less than the critical value of 't' at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the relation can be strong and insignificant. There is an impact of capital structure towards the EPS of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.

Hypothesis 2 (H₂): There is no impact of Capital Structure Leverage towards the Return on Investment of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.

Table 12, Correlation and t test results for ROA and Capital Structure Leverages of APSFC

	't' value	Correlation result	'r' value	Hypothesis result
Debt Equity Ratio	-0.26	Positive and insignificant	//1.97//	Accepted
Debt Ratio	0.054	Positive and insignificant	//0.15//	Accepted
Proprietary Ratio	-0.21	Positive and insignificant	//0.60//	Accepted

Source: Computed

Table 12 depicts that the Correlation between ROA and Capita structure leverage ratios of APSFC. It can be seen that capital structure and leverages showed negative relationship with ROA. t-test results, It is clear that the computed value of hypothesis is less than the critical value of 't' at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the relation can be weak and insignificant. There is impact of Capital Structure Leverage towards the Return on Investment.

Hypothesis 3 (H₃): There is no impact of Working Capital towards the Return on Investment of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.

Table 13, Correlation and t test results for ROA and Working Capital Ratios of APSFC

	't' value	Correlation result	'r' value	Hypothesis result
Current Ratio	-0.095	Positive and insignificant	//0.76//	Accepted
Cash Ratio	-0.39	Positive and insignificant	//1.20//	Accepted

Source: Computed

Table 13 depicts that the Correlation between ROA and working capital ratios of APSFC. It can be seen that capital structure and liquidity showed negative relationship with ROA. t-test results, It is clear that the computed value of hypothesis is less than the critical value of 't' at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the relation can be weak and insignificant. There is impact of working capital ratios towards the Return on Investment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

The capital structure policy deals with aspects like the proportion of debt and equity to finance the company's operation. The decision to build a capital structure that is optimal is significant in the process of achieving the objectives of wealth maximization of the company. It is a well known fact that the financial decision of any corporation is a complex affair which involves the analysis of different variables. The present study tries to analyze the capital structure, Earnings per Share and Return on Assets of the APSFC. It has since long been facing various problems and various factors were taken into consideration during the study to analyze the impact of Debt Fund, Financial Leverage and working capital on profitability. From the study, the observations have been done. It is observed that major source of equity fund is reserves and surplus. Overall debt structure during the study period, major source of debt funds is long term borrowings. It is observed that more than 80 percent of assets are finance by debt funds. This is not good sign of profitability. Debt equity Ratio of the corporation was on an average 1.23 times. It can be seen that corporation shows good solvency position, as capital milk mainly contributed by Debt Funds, whereas participation of shareholders' fund is almost equal. Average current Ratio was 0.82 times, which is lower than the ideal current ratio, i.e. 2 times (2:1) Cash and a lower portion in Total Assets; during the study period only 0.5 percent of cash of its total assets has been maintained by the corporation. APSFC is a sound profitable position as its average Return on assets ratio was 3.02 times of its investment during the study period. Earnings per Share of the corporation are only 0.47 per share only. For the testing of hypotheses, correlation and multiple regressions have been used. The result of first hypothesis, It proved that capital structure is influenced to the earnings per share. The second hypothesis is of the study is also proved that debt funds are significant source to the profitability. Working capital is also one of the parameter to attain optimum profit; It is proved by the third hypothesis.

SUGGESTIONS:

To conclude, our finding from the capital structure and financial performance of APSFC is satisfactory during the study period. It suggests that the purpose of borrowing funds could be achieved since heavy borrowings led to increase in EPS. Corporation should try to achieve optimum capital structure. It is used as source of finance. It saves a considerable amount in payment of tax, an interest is allowed as deductible expenses in computation of tax. Hence, the effective cost of debt is reduced, called tax leverage. It is suggested that APSFC should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, debt and improve the productive efficiency of employees. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the corporation for better performance.

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